

ORGANOMETALLIC COMPOUNDS OF THE ALLYL RADICAL. PART II* TIN TETRA ALLYL AND ITS DERIVATIVES

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Tin tetra-allyl has been isolated by the action of allyl magnesium bromide on stannic halides. By the action of bromine on the substance, tin triallyl bromide and by the action of stannic bromide, tin diallyl dibromide have been prepared. A pyridine derivative of the latter is also described.

Though a large number of organic compounds of tin are described in the literature (Goddard and Goddard, "Text Books of Inorganic Chemistry" Vol. XI, Organo-Metallic Compounds : p. 300 and *et. seq.*) the only reference to an organic compound of tin where the allyl radical is involved is to allyl stannonic acid, $\text{CH}_2 : \text{CH}.\text{CH}_2$. $\text{Sn} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \text{OH} \end{array}$ (Lesbre and Glotz, *Compt. rend.*, 1934, 198, 1426) which corresponds to $\text{CH}_2 : \text{CH}.\text{CH}_2$. $\text{C} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \text{OH} \end{array}$.

Tin tetra-allyl has been prepared by the action of allyl magnesium bromide on stannic chloride (*cf.* Pope and Peachey, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 19, 290 ; Pfeiffer and Schnurmann, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 320).

The weight of magnesium taken is twice the theoretical amount for the allyl bromide in order to prevent the Wurtz reaction (*cf.* Gilman and Mac-Glumphy, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1928, *iv*, 43, 1322) taking place.

The amount of allyl magnesium bromide used is twice the theoretical quantity to prevent the formation of any tin triallyl halide. The use of stannic bromide gave a lower yield of tin tetraallyl.

Tin tetra-alkyls are acted upon by the halogens, especially by bromine and iodine, the halogens displacing the alkyl radicals and forming tin trialkyl halides or tin dialkyl dihalides depending upon the amount of halogen used (Krause and Sessions, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2381 ; Goddard and Goddard, *loc. cit.*). Tin tetra-allyl decolourises solutions of bromine in carbon tetrachloride and carbon disulphide. Even when theoretical quantities for the formation of tin triallyl bromide,

are used, traces of tin diallyl dibromide are also formed, and the separation of the two has not been possible. The use of pyridine as the solvent in the bromination of tin tetra-allyl (*cf.* Krause, *Ber.*, 1918, 51, 912) does not improve the purity of the product.

Kozesckow (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, B, 1661) has studied the action of stannic halides on tin tetra-alkyls in detail and has prepared tin alkyl halides by this method.

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Tin tetra-allyl reacts with tin tetrabromide with evolution of heat. Curiously enough tin diallyl dibromide seems to be the main product of the reaction even when theoretical quantities according to the reaction, $3 \text{Sn}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4 + \text{SnBr}_4 \rightarrow 4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{SnBr}$ are employed. The reaction,

also does not yield pure tin triallyl bromide. Tin diallyl dibromide appears to be found with considerable ease but not the monobromide.

Attempts to prepare tin triallyl hydroxide (cf. Grüttner and Krause, *Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1802) and fluoride (cf. Krause, *Ber.*, 1918, 51, 1447) from the impure tin triallyl bromide, and tin triallyl iodide by iodination (Goddard and Goddard, *loc. cit.*) of tin tetra-allyl have been unsuccessful.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—In some of the experiments described, B. D. H. allyl bromide was redistilled and used, but on account of the difficulty of obtaining this compound locally, allyl alcohol was prepared from glycerol and oxalic acid and it was converted into allyl bromide

FIG. 1

(*Organic Synthesis*, I, 3; Vanino, *Präparative Chemie*, II, 27). Commercial ether made anhydrous by the usual procedure was collected by distilling directly into a long cylindrical funnel f_1 (Fig. 1) from which it was directly added to the flask F_1 (F in figure stands for F_1 , F_2 and F_3) in which the Grignard reagent was prepared. Stannic chloride was prepared according to the usual method (*Präparative Chemie*, I, p. 594), rectified and distilled in all-glass vessels under reduced pressure and sucked up into weighed glass capsules with capillary necks and sealed. Stannic bromide was prepared by the action of bromine on tin (*Präparative Chemie*, I, 596) and distilled, the fraction distilling at 201° being collected and kept in sealed glass tubes. B.D.H. Analar petroleum ether, b.p. $60-80^\circ$, kept over sodium wire and distilled before use, was employed as the solvent for the stannic chloride.

Isolation of Tin Tetra-allyl.—Dry ether was distilled into the funnel f_1 and about 50 c.c. of it were added to the flask F_1 containing 14.8 g. of magnesium turnings. 26 C.c. (37.2 g.) of allyl bromide were measured into the remaining ether (about 100 c.c.) in f_1 . The stirrer, S, was started and the ethereal solution of allyl bromide was added dropwise to the magnesium keeping the flask F_1 in iced water to prevent the ether refluxing rather violently. Throughout the experiment pure, dry hydrogen was passed into the apparatus. The addition of allyl bromide took about an hour and a half. The ethereal solution was refluxed for 1 hour and then cooled. The flask F_1 was carefully removed from the apparatus and another flask F_2 of the same size slipped in to prevent the Grignard reagent solution sticking to the sides of the stirrer undergoing decomposition. F_1 was immediately closed with a two holed cork one hole fitted with a tube connected to a source of pure dry hydrogen and another with a tube bent twice at right angles, the second arm carrying a cork fitting a third flask F_3 of exactly the same sized neck as F_1 . To a second hole in the cork fitting F_3 a calcium chloride guard tube was fixed. The ethereal solution of the Grignard reagent in F_1 was forced out by pressure of hydrogen into F_2 in order to separate it from the excess of the magnesium turnings. F_1 was then removed from the apparatus and F_3 slid in position. f_1 was then replaced by the funnel f_2 containing petroleum ether. The end of the capillary c passing through tap t was broken by turning the tap and 10 grams of stannic chloride in it driven into the petroleum ether by warming the upper part of c . The Grignard reagent in F_2 was cooled with iced water and stannic chloride solution added drop by drop with stirring. A white solid separated immediately which disappeared on stirring. After all the stannic chloride solution had been added, the mixture was refluxed for 1 hour, the coil condenser C set for downward distillation, and the ether distilled off. The flask and contents were then warmed to about 70° in order to complete the reaction between the stannic halide and the Grignard reagent and to convert any triallyl halide formed into tin tetra-allyl by the excess of the Grignard reagent (*vide Discussion*). F_2 was then cooled in ice and salt and the distillate of ether and petroleum ether poured back into it, and ice-cold water added little by little with vigorous stirring. Cold dilute hydrochloric acid (about 3%) was added until the contents of the flask gave two clear layers and the solid deposited on hydrolysis had dissolved. The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether, and dried over calcium chloride.

As the liquid underwent decomposition above 200° it was purified by distilling at reduced pressure from a small bulb with a wide side tube placed near the neck as condenser b.p. $69-70^\circ/1.5$ mm. The hot vapours of the liquid were noticed to attack rubber.

Samples of the redistilled substance were analysed. The tin was converted into stannic chloride by heating with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube in boiling water and precipitated as stannic sulphide and roasted to stannic oxide. In some of the estimations the tin was directly precipitated as metastannic acid but this method gave lower values, probably because some tin was retained as ammonium hexachlorostannate (*cf.* Jelley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 580). The carbon and hydrogen were estimated by mixing the substance with cupric oxide and "combusting" as usual. [Found: C, 50.99, 51.21; H, 7.22, 7.14; Sn, 43.36, 42.45; M.W., 286.8, 273.4. Sn (C₄H₈)₄ requires C, 50.93; H, 7.13; Sn, 41.98 per cent. M.W., 282.7].

The yield of tin tetra-allyl was 85% of the theory, calculated on the weight of stannic chloride. When stannic bromide was used the yield was only about 60% of the theoretical. Some high boiling hydrocarbon was also obtained.

Tin tetra-allyl is a colourless, highly refractive mobile liquid with a slightly unpleasant odour similar to that of tin tetraethyl. Continued smelling caused sneezing. It is soluble in all the common organic solvents and in concentrated aqueous alcohol. It is immiscible with water, and the aqueous suspension on keeping becomes turbid. On cooling in solid carbon dioxide and ether, it does not crystallise but becomes very viscous.

On exposing a drop of tin tetra-allyl in a watch glass for a day it leaves a residue of stannic oxide, but the substance can be kept in sealed tubes for many weeks without any visible change. It burns with a luminous flame forming fumes of stannic oxide. It decolourises solutions of bromine and iodine instantaneously. It is decomposed by concentrated mineral acids evolving propylene, which has been identified by bromination, when propylene dibromide, a liquid with a sweetish odour, b.p. 142°, is obtained. With concentrated nitric acid, stannic oxide is precipitated. With fuming nitric acid, the substance inflames with violent reaction leaving a residue of stannic oxide.

Density was determined with a small Hare's apparatus the readings being taken with a travelling microscope and the refractive index was determined with a small hollow prism, $n_D^{20.5} = 1.243$; $n_D^{32} = 1.533$; $n_D^{52} = 1.526$. Molecular refraction (from Lorentz and Lorenz's formula) for D line = 70.69. Molecular refraction for H line = 69.9. Calculated using Eisenlohr's (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, 75, 585) values for D line = 71.56; for H_α line = 71.02.

Halogen Derivatives

Action of Halogens on Tin Tetra-allyl.—Tin tetra-allyl (5 g.) dissolved in carbon tetrachloride (25 c.c.) was brominated with an approximately N/2 solution of bromine in carbon tetrachloride. Both the solutions were first cooled to about -15° with ice and salt. When all the materials were quite dry, a clear solution with a slight yellow tinge was obtained. The carbon tetrachloride was distilled off from a water-bath. A few drops of allyl bromide also distilled at about 70°. This product was distilled at 73-75°/1.5 mm. The liquid seemed to be impure tin triallyl bromide, with tin diallyl dibromide present as an impurity (as shown by analysis for bromine and tin) and it often gave some scaly crystals with pyridine, which is also characteristic of the dibromo compound (*vide infra*).

This impure tin triallyl bromide possesses a very penetrating odour. It is miscible with all the common organic solvents. Water immediately precipitates an insoluble white solid. On exposing it for a few minutes needle-like crystals in aborescent formation (probably $[(C_3H_5)_3SnOH]_x \cdot (C_3H_5)_3SnBr$ formed by the loss of the hydrogen bromide) are obtained. (*cf.* Krause and Sessions, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2361). Unlike the other tin trialkyl bromides, this substance did not give any definite compound when pure dry ammonia gas was passed into an ethereal solution. Only a gelatinous precipitate of indefinite composition was formed.

The bromination was conducted using carbon disulphide for pyridine as the solvent and in each case the product was impure tin triallyl bromide. Bromination, when carried out at the temperature of carbon dioxide snow and ether, produced similarly impure reaction products.

The action of iodine on tin tetra-allyl was tried using theoretical quantities of the reactants in carbon tetrachloride solution, both the solutions being cooled in ice and salt. As the iodine solution was being added it was found that some amorphous solid was separating. On distilling off the carbon tetrachloride, a large amount of amorphous solid separated. This was filtered off. A faintly yellow liquid with a very strong penetrating odour was obtained. But solid matter began to separate from the liquid again. Probably the liquid was tin triallyl iodide, which was not stable. Also it did not form any crystalline derivative with ammonia or any amino compound like the other trialkyl iodides of tin (Goddard and Goddard, *loc. cit.*).

Action of Stannic Bromide on Tin Tetra-allyl: Formation of Tin Diallyl Bromide.—To tin tetra-allyl (3.5 g.) in carbon tetrachloride (15 c.c.) stannic bromide (5.4 g.) dissolved in the same volume of carbon tetrachloride was added and the tube containing the mixture was cooled, evacuated to about 2. c.m. pressure, sealed and kept at 50° in a liquid bath for about 10 hours. At the end of the period a test portion showed the presence of free stannic bromide. A few more drops of tin tetra-allyl were added and the heating continued for about 8 hours at the end of which period no free stannic bromide could be detected. On distilling off the carbon tetrachloride under reduced pressure a liquid, b.p. 77-79°/2 mm. was obtained. [Found: Sn, 32.56; Br, 43.95. $(C_3H_5)_2SnBr_2$ requires Sn, 32.93; Br, 44.32 per cent].

Tin diallyl dibromide is a light yellow coloured, highly refracting, dense oil with a faintly unpleasant odour. It is soluble in all the common organic solvents. It is decomposed by water and mineral acids. It gives crystalline derivatives with amines.

Pyridine Derivative of Tin Diallyl Dibromide.—To tin diallyl dibromide cooled in water, pyridine was added little by little until there was a faint smell of pyridine. More or less the whole mass solidified. The flat tabular crystals were filtered, washed with a little pyridine, pressed between filter papers and dried over calcium chloride *in vacuo*. The substance melts at 99° (decomp.) with previous softening. The compound is highly soluble in pyridine and decomposes on keeping for some time giving a rather penetrating odour and leaving behind a residue insoluble in pyridine. [Found: Sn, 22.99; Br, 30.79; N, 5.32. $(C_3H_5)_2SnBr_2 \cdot 2C_5H_5N$ requires Sn, 22.89; Br, 30.81; N, 5.41 per cent].

Tin diallyl dibromide gave a crystalline derivative with aniline also. It is very unstable. The compound, rendered free from aniline, gave differing values on analyses, and it contained an insoluble matter also indicating decomposition.

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